

Utilization of fruit waste and recycled paper for bioplastic synthesis

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Abstract

Based on current events, bioplastic is a better option in terms of being eco-friendly and not harming the environment. Plastic, on the other hand, cause more problems to the world rather than solutions. This article is about learning the compatibility of a variety of fruit waste and paper for bioplastic synthesis and utilizing it for a better purpose. Throughout, the researchers have already concluded that by using different available fruit waste, there will be some fruit waste with zero starch content. Therefore, the researchers will add starch to the mixture. The researchers will also add glycerol as a plasticizer. The design study is quantitative research. The research involves using equipment and method to collect data such as the researcher's way of finding the tensile strength of the output, biodegradability, water solubility test, and survey to find out the perspective of the respondents in terms of flexibility, scent/odor, texture, sturdiness, and overall appearance of the output we provided them. The independent variable is the amount of starch and we soon discovered that the thickness also affects the tensile strength and flexibility. For the controlled variable, it will be the amount of fruit waste and glycerol. Then lastly, the dependent variable will be the tensile strength and flexibility. The researchers have high hopes for the outcome of the research. The procedure and the approach of this study were inspired by previous research. This study aims to help those people who are badly affected by plastic. The researchers aim to accomplish this study that can help to guide the path for future developments and solutions.

Keywords: Utilization; Fruit waste; Recycled paper; Bioplastic synthesis.

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Introduction

Plastic and garbage wastes are gradually increasing throughout the years. Some of the reasons involved the irresponsibility of the people and undisciplined citizens. If psychological correctness cannot be accomplished, the other aspect must be altered. Moreover, discipline cannot be fully observed from citizens all over the country, and garbage scattered across our lands is solid proof.

Fruit waste and paper are common garbage waste that we can find elsewhere. Garbage is often thrown away without thinking about recycling it or its possible uses. Students are a viable source of paper. Once used during a review, quiz, and other schoolwork, it is often thrown away or ignited. Fruit wastes, on the other hand, are solid wastes which is one of the community health problems (Ritchie & Hoser, 2018).

The amount of garbage and plastic waste in the community is gradually increasing throughout the decades. Biodegradable waste increases with the rising population. For that reason, the researchers wanted to find a way to make the product work the same way as plastic but can decompose and dissolve in time that would not harm other living creatures (Arikan & Bilgen, 2019).

The desire to produce a product from garbage or recycled materials into a solution that can help reduce waste in our community and as an alternative to plastic. Therefore, the researchers wanted to develop a material that can be made out of simple household products like the main materials which are fruit waste and paper. Bioplastic is a biodegradable plastic that functions as an alternative to petroleum-based plastic. It replicates the conventional plastic but is made from organic materials hence can decompose in less than a year (Acciona, n.d.).

Improper garbage waste disposal is inevitable. Solid waste is one of the community's health problems which includes biodegradable waste such as fruit waste and papers. Moreover, discipline cannot be fully observed by citizens all over the country, and garbage scattered across our lands is solid proof. Humans are the reason why innocent animals get disrupted and disturbed. It is very unfair for animals to suffer from ignorant and undisciplined acts of humans. Most people can easily waste and throw paper after being used regardless of the billions of trees being cut down to make paper each year.

Bakelite was the first synthetic plastic that was produced in 1907. It is the beginning of the global plastic industry. However, the rapid growth of plastic pollution was not realized until the 1950s. Plastic waste determines its risk of entering the ocean. Approximately 80 percent of ocean plastics came from land-based sources, and 20 percent from marine sources.

Plastics are strong and buoyant that show resilience in the marine environment, allowing the plastic to be transported over far distances. The Great Pacific Garbage Patch is a collection of marine debris in the North Pacific Ocean. Marine debris is litter that ends up in oceans, seas, and other large bodies of water. It is the largest accumulation of ocean plastic in the world. It is like an island full of plastic floating in the ocean (The Ocean Cleanup, n.d.).

The researchers want to make this product to make a solution that can reduce waste in the community. Fruit peels are generally found in houses, cafeterias, and markets as waste and ready to be discarded. As well as papers from students after school year or even scratch papers that they had used to solve math solutions. Virgin papers or clean white papers are used once after it was written like most plastics that are only used once.

Intelligently using these materials converted into a product that can be a potential solution to one of the leading problems the world faces or plastic pollution by simply reusing fruit peels, the amount of waste in households may be decreased, and using recycled papers minimize logging, deforestation and help the environment (Kale et al., 2007). The researchers plan to make bioplastic using combinations of fruit waste that everyone can easily buy and afford. Examples are wastes from orange, tangerine, watermelons, melons, lemons, mangos, and pomelos. The recycled papers, on the other hand, is added to the mixture before it solidifies. It will increase the amount of the product, reduce garbage waste, making good use of recycled papers. Based on research, it can make the output more durable.

Bioplastic is simply plastic produced from organic compounds that can decompose shorter than petroleum-based plastic. It will serve some functions similar to plastic that people widely used today. Bioplastic can be used in people's daily lives based on how it will be made and produced (Gibbens, 2018). For example, if it is thin and flexible, consumers can use it as a bag or a carrying container just like plastic bags for simple things they possess. With precise amounts and accurate components, it can be formed into containers or trays, household equipment, or even pots for gardening (Goodall, 2011).

The bioplastic can also serve benefits with inputs it requires. Papers are widely used without the thought of recycling them after. Fruit waste will be used up to its full potential. Instead of immediately throwing it away, it can be reused to a material that will be further used.

One thing is certain, the product will help reduce garbage waste in our community and try to replace plastic for everyday use. In other words, we want to hit two birds with one stone which are reducing solid waste in our community and utilizing fruit waste and paper to produce bioplastic (European Bioplastics, 2016).

Research Problem

This study is aimed to produce an efficient and functional bioplastic from fruit waste and recycled papers. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions.

1. Can the bioplastic be effectively developed from recycled paper and fruit waste of tangerine, orange, lemon, pomelo, watermelon, melon, ripe and unripe mango?

2. Is the bioplastic made from recycled paper and fruit waste of lemon, orange, watermelon, melon, unripe and ripe mango, and pomelo able to meet the parameters in terms of:
 - 2.1 Tensile Strength
 - 2.2 Water Solubility
 - 2.3 Biodegradability
3. What is the perception of the respondents of the product in terms of:
 - 3.1 Flexibility
 - 3.2 Scent/Odor
 - 3.3 Texture
 - 3.4 Sturdiness
 - 3.5 Overall Appearance

Significance of the Study

Students. Students use a huge amount of paper in their everyday classes. Most of them are used just once and they are immediately thrown away afterward. Sadly, papers are not put to good use and students have not thought of recycling them. It will benefit a lot of people by giving them knowledge and opportunities by providing the best function of ordinary material. Informing the audience to accumulate papers to be recycled not just to be another scratch paper but also a component of bioplastic that can be used to improve its strength and increase its content.

Community. It has already been proven that some fruits like bananas, which are rich in starch, can be used to produce bioplastic. Some fruit peels which have a low amount of starch content like citrus fruits are not used widely to produce bioplastic (Fabunmi et al., 2006). In this research, the researchers want to give their audience an explanation and method in using a combination of fruit waste to produce bioplastic. Most fruit wastes are thrown away due to the lack of information and strategies in making so much use of the little things around us. People usually see research about fertilizers, repellants, and perfumes but this research will give a different way of putting fruit waste to good use that can also help the community.

Environment. Petroleum-based plastic with direct exposure to the sun can release powerful greenhouse gasses and produce heat. In some cases, plastic in the ocean heats up and affects the surrounding water. Just by producing bioplastic, we can reduce greenhouse gas emissions that badly affect the environment. Because of the great heat that can cause the animals to lose their habitats and experience dehydration, it will be hard for them to live. With that being said, it is a chain of reactions or events that kept worsening the impacts of using plastic. So, by pursuing and continuing this study, it can serve as a steppingstone towards the development of what we want to achieve in our research.

Scope and Limitations

Bioplastic will be based on recycled papers and maximizing the possible uses of fruit waste, in that case, the bioplastic will be cheaper. Because the bioplastic is made out of organic materials, it will have lists of limitations, but the researchers found ways on how the product can reach people's expectations.

To make the product more tensile, the process also includes adding starch that will also act as a glue to hold the fruit waste and recycled paper. For the flexibility of the bioplastic, the researchers will add glycerol that will act as a plasticizer. The prototype is tested in terms of its tensile strength or the limited weight the bioplastic can withstand. The biodegradability and solubility test will be conducted to learn the properties of the product if it can be dissolved in water and degrade within the given period. The thickness cannot be identified because the flattening is manual work and precision cannot be fully observed hence there is inconsistency throughout the output. Therefore, the researchers conducted several trials in testing the output wherein each sample came from a different experiment, consequently, it has different thickness.

In this study, the researchers would not use the process called sterilization instead the researchers will use pasteurization. And also, the researchers would not add fragrance boosters. This research, proving the possibility of using recycled paper and combination fruit waste such as lemon peels, watermelon and melon rinds, orange and tangerine peels, pomelo wastes, ripe and unripe mangos that can be used to produce bioplastic under accurate and appropriate proportions. Lastly, as the research not using sterilization, the final product will only be shaped like a paper bag.

Methodology

Research Instrument and Ingredients

The following are the equipment, tools, and ingredients used in the experiment.

1. Oven or natural heat to evaporate liquids
2. Gas stove or rice cooker to boil and soften the fruit peels
3. Blender to grind the softened fruit waste and paper
4. Containers that can withstand the heat
5. Containers for fruit peels and papers during experiment
6. Spatula or spoons for scooping quantities
7. Wedges to reduce the size of fruit peels and paper
8. Strainer for filtration of water
9. Tongs for transferring of ingredients
10. Storage box for fruit waste and recycled papers
11. Parchment paper
12. Rolling pin
13. Cutting mat
14. Weighing scale
15. Recycled paper
16. Water
17. Starch
18. Glycerol as plasticizer (for plastic-like output)
19. Fruit waste such as: Orange, Tangerine, Watermelon, Melon, Lemon, Ripe and Unripe Mangos, and Pomelo.

Research Locale

The research is conducted in Ligas, Bacoor City and Meadowood Executive Village. The survey is conducted on the students of St. Dominic College Basic Education located at Emilio Aguinaldo Highway, Bacoor, 4102, Cavite.

Procedure

The following are a step-by-step procedures for producing bioplastic.

1. **Gathering.** The researchers gathered papers from finished schoolwork and scratch papers. For fruit waste, the researchers provided containers to store the fruit peels and put them inside the freezer to remain in good condition. This is the first step in every experimentation. Gathering the materials first before proceeding to the actual making of the bioplastic. Since the ingredients are based on recycled materials and garbage waste, the researchers have to collate it ahead of time to be all set before conducting. In the past few weeks, recycled papers from roleplay scripts, invalid printing, scratch papers, and many more have been already collected.
2. **Preparing.** All the ingredients needed are laid on the table. This way, it is convenient for the researchers since all the materials needed are easily distinguishable and visible to the researchers.
3. **Cutting.** Paper can be reduced into smaller pieces just by using scissors to cut them. Fruit peels, on the other hand, require knives and a cutting mat to cut or to reduce their sizes. To soften the fruit peels faster, it needs to be sliced into small portions for the heat to spread easily and evenly. The papers will also be cut down into smaller pieces and will be placed in a container filled with room temperature water.
4. **Pasteurization.** The fruit peels will be boiled because of their durability and be prepared for grinding. Some fruit waste is difficult to grind therefore, the researchers are required to soften the fruit waste through boiling. This process must be supervised all the time since it deals with heat and might over soften the fruit peels. The papers will not be boiled because of their fragileness.
5. **Grinding.** The ingredients will be ground or mashed to levigate the pieces. By doing this it will help form container-like and other shapes better, by allowing the ingredients to integrate well with each other. This is done by putting the softened fruit peels, papers, and enough water in a blender. This process must be supervised to check if the fruit waste and papers are ground well and minute enough to proceed to step 6.
6. **Filtration.** Before placing it inside the oven, the liquid content must be reduced to lessen the time of evaporating. Heat has something to do to get this part done and the researchers can manually remove the excess liquids by straining the water. As much as possible in able for the process to be successful, the mixed ingredients need to be desiccated.
7. **Adding Starch and Glycerol.** After removing excess liquids add the right amount of starch and glycerol. These are additive components that will make the output more functional.
8. **Transferring.** After dehydrating the ingredients, the researchers will transfer them to a container or any molder to achieve the shape that can carry objects. This will serve as the platform where the bioplastic can now be solidified. The mixture is placed between parchment papers and must be flattened by using a rolling pin. After that, it is placed on a baking sheet before putting inside the oven.

9. **Drying.** The oven will be the tool to evaporate the excess liquid. This process must be under complete supervision since it deals with electricity and avoid burning the mixture. Letting it sit under the sun or using an oven to speed the procedure can help with the drying of the mixture. Waiting for minutes or hours until it completely hardens depending on what method you chose to do. In using the oven method, the researchers need to be careful and supervise to prevent burning the product.
10. **Testing.** The testing involves tensile test, biodegradable test, water solubility test, and survey about its flexibility, scent/odor, texture, sturdiness, and overall appearance.
11. **Shaping.** The final output is shaped like the paper bag we usually use.

Research Design

Quantitative research is used that includes surveys, measurements, and other equipment to collect numerical or measurable data. The study uses an experimental research design. It aims to learn the capability and functionality of fruit waste and recycled paper for bioplastic synthesis.

Data Analysis Procedure

Tensile Test

Most researchers used a technique wherein they hook the object into the output allowing it to gain cleavage or increase its probability of breaking and it is not how we normally use plastic bags, for that reason, the researchers will design a model to test the tensile strength of the output. The model is designed to replicate how we use plastic by hanging the output and applying force by adding objects with substantial weight. Additionally, the model will test the product the same way as to how we use plastic as a container or a bag.

Since the researchers do not possess Testometric machine or expensive equipment. The film samples were tested by hanging the output with clamps on both ends. The weight was applied at the center of the hanged prototype. Weight is added until the bioplastic broke. The final weight will be recorded as the weight of limitation of the bioplastic. Weight or object is weighed before applying it to the bioplastic prototype. The researchers supervised and waited for the bioplastic to respond but if the bioplastic remained from its initial position and did not break, fall, and still in one piece, the researchers applied another object with significant weight, then the cycle continues.

Water Solubility Test

The film samples were cut into square sections of 6x8 cm, and the dry film mass was weighed accurately and recorded. The samples remained immersed in 100 mL distilled water was carried out for 36 hours (Marichelvam et al., 2019). The lasting portions of the film were filtered after 36 hours. They were then dried in a hot air oven at 110°C until a fixed weight was found. The percentage of total soluble matter (% solubility) was calculated as $WS (\%) = [(W_0 - W_i)/W_0] \times 100$, where WS is solubility in water; W_0 is the weight at the beginning of the bioplastics, and W_i is the final weight of the bioplastics (Marichelvam et al., 2019).

The average results will be identified by the equation: $\text{mean} = \frac{\text{summation of all values}}{\text{number of values}}$. Where the result of all trials will be added and divided by the number of trials.

Biodegradability Test

The specimen was cut into pieces of 6x8 cm. Found near the roots of plants that are rich in nitrogenous bacteria, 500 g of soil (having slight moisture content) was collected and stored in a container. The sample was underneath the soil for 100 hours. The weight of the specimen was measured before and after the testing. The biodegradability test was measured by Equation: $\text{Weight Loss (\%)} = [(W_0 - W)/W_0] \times 100$, where W_0 and W are the weights of samples before and after the test (Marichelvam et al., 2019). The average results will be identified by the equation: $\text{mean} = \frac{\text{summation of all values}}{\text{number of values}}$, where the result of all trials will be added and divided by the number of trials.

Survey

Flexibility, Scent/Odor, Texture, Sturdiness, and Overall Appearance are gathered through a survey. The said categories were conducted and rated from 1 to 5. For flexibility, the respondents rate it from 1 or very unsatisfied to 5 or very satisfied. For scent/odor, the respondents rate it from 1 or very unpleasant to 5 or very pleasant. For texture, the respondents rate it from 1 or very rough to 5 or very smooth. For sturdiness and overall appearance, the respondents rate it from 1 or very poor to 5 or excellent. We used the Likert scale for our survey. The rate was measured by the equation: $\text{Rate (\%)} = \frac{\text{Percentage}}{\text{Base}} \times 100$, where the percentage is the number of people who answered the specific option and base is the total respondents. The mean was measured by the equation: $\text{mean} = \frac{\text{summation of all values}}{\text{number of values}}$.

Results and Discussion

The researchers garnered all the desired data with the help of the previous studies on how they do and test the tensile strength, biodegradability, and water solubility. The previous research that is similar to the researchers' study is the banana bioplastic in which the former researchers used antioxidants and preservatives that would increase the biodegradation period of plastic (Manimaran et al., 2016). The researchers can sum these methods up to have a better product that will be suitable to all users. For the researchers who want to have a successful outcome of the product that can inspire others hence the researchers should not only be based on their understanding because with lack of research and no proven supposition, but it will also be difficult to experiment without a promising outcome. Their theories and findings are most important to the researchers thus developing and improving their works, and not committing mistakes during the process. The previous researchers only worked with a specific fruit waste, but our team used a combination of fruit waste that is not yet proven, and some have no starch content to test and substantiate that they are capable of being converted into bioplastic. The researchers also have learned that the use of glycerol for the product can serve as the polymer for plastic or plasticizer. At the very beginning of the research, the researchers did not include the use of glycerol. Therefore, the first experimentation was not flexible as the product that has glycerol.

The use of glycerol was already proven by the previous researchers and with a validated analysis, we found out that the result of our third experimentation had achieved our expectations. Adding an appropriate amount of starch during the third experiment led us to our final product with an accurate and proportional amount of starch and glycerol.

Evaluation

Tensile Test

Table 1. Result of tensile test of bioplastic

Parameter	Limited Weight (in grams)
1st Trial	less than 4500
2nd Trial	less than 5400

Based on the results, the first sample is thinner hence the limited weight is lowered compared to the second sample and the second sample is thicker hence the limited weight is higher compared to the first sample. Both samples have the same amount of glycerol and starch, but the thickness is different. We found out from this test that the thinness or thickness of the bioplastic affects the tensile strength of the output.

Figure 1. (left) 1st trial, (right) 2nd trial

Water Solubility Test

Table 2. Results of water solubility test of bioplastic

Parameter	Initial weight (in grams)	Final weight (in grams)	Solubility (%)
1st Trial	5.5	3.4	38.18
2nd Trial	3.7	2.4	35.14
3rd Trial	2.3	1.6	30.43
4th Trial	1.6	1.1	31.25
5th Trial	1.9	1.3	31.58
Average	3	1.96	33.32

Over time, the water where the samples were dissolved is noticeably gained a greenish color. From the first hours, the water is light green but after a while or more than 20 hours, the water is visibly green. The bioplastic samples became soft and can easily be destroyed or broken down into pieces. Additionally, it can certainly be torn apart manually. It lost weight that ranges from 30% to 38% in 36 hours underwater and an average of 33.32%. By these results, the bioplastic is soluble in water.

Figure 2. (left) 2nd hour of the test, (right) 36th hour of the test

Biodegradability Test

Table 3. Results of biodegradability test of bioplastic

Parameter	Initial weight (in grams)	Final weight (in grams)	Solubility (%)
1st Trial	10.4	9.8	5.77
2nd Trial	8.6	8.2	4.65
3rd Trial	9.7	9.3	4.12
Average	9.57	9.1	4.85

After 100 hours beneath the soil, there are noticeable black, white, and yellow spots that show microorganism interrogation. It lost about 4% to 6% of weight or an average of 4.85%. In conclusion, the bioplastic is biodegradable and additionally, our product did not undergo sterilization, it has bacteria and spores of its own and can speed up the process of degrading.

Figure 3. (left) 1st trial outcome, (middle) 2nd trial outcome, (right) 3rd trial outcome

Flexibility

Out of 35 respondents, 11 answered very satisfied, 19 answered satisfied, five (5) respondents answered fair, and no respondents answered unsatisfied and very unsatisfied. Figure 4 below shows the rate of the result for flexibility.

Flexibility in bioplastic can be achieved by adding glycerol proportional to the amount of fruit waste. Adding more glycerol to make it more flexible will only waste resources hence the flexibility can only be altered by producing an output thin enough to be flexible like the petroleum-based plastic. Thin output can make the bioplastic less tensile but more flexible and thick output can make the bioplastic less flexible but more tensile.

Figure 4. Result of the survey for flexibility in percentage

Figure 6. Result of the survey for texture in percentage

Scent/Odor

Out of 35 respondents, seven (7) answered very pleasant, 20 answered pleasant, eight (8) respondents answered neutral, and no respondents answered unpleasant and very unpleasant. The figure below shows the rate of the result for scent/odor.

Figure 5. Result of the survey for scent/odor in percentage

The odor is still debatable; thus some people claimed that it smells disgusting while some people claimed that it smells like tea. We do not use any odor enhancers, because in this research we only used pasteurization hence bacteria can multiply and cause unpleasant odor quicker than bioplastic that was sterilized. Sterilization and odor enhancers are a pair and must be done both for future research.

Texture

Out of 35 respondents, two (2) answered very smooth, seven (7) answered smooth, fourteen (14) respondents answered fair, twelve (12) respondents answered rough, and no respondents answered very rough. Figure 6 shows the rate of the result for texture.

The texture of our bioplastic depends on how minute the fruit wastes are. Most respondents answered "rough" since some of the fruit waste is not minute well enough or broken down into tiny pieces. Smooth bioplastic can be achieved by grinding or powdering the fruit waste. In conclusion, more time inside the blender can produce a smoother bioplastic.

Sturdiness

Out of 35 respondents, 12 answered excellent, 16 answered good, seven (7) respondents answered fair, and no respondents answered poor and very poor. The figure below shows the rate of the result for sturdiness.

Figure 7. Result of the survey for sturdiness in percentage

Based on their answers, majority of the respondents answered good which means that the respondents are satisfied with the output we provided them. The answers only revolve around fair, good, and excellent.

Overall Appearance

Figure 8. Result of the survey for overall appearance in percentage

Out of 35 respondents, 15 answered excellent, 15 answered good, five (5) respondents answered fair, and no respondents answered poor and very poor. The figure above shows the rate of the result for sturdiness. The hue of our bioplastic is in the shade of green. The color, texture, and scent affect this category. By these results, the researchers can still improve its overall appearance by the texture and color consistency, and its odor.

Mean

Figure 9. Mean of the results of the survey from count

The mean for flexibility is 3.885 and when rounded off it is under satisfactory, 3.971 for scent, and when rounded off it is under pleasant, 2.971 for texture and when rounded off it is under rough, 4.1428 for sturdiness and when rounded off it is under good, and 4.285 for overall appearance and when rounded off it is under good.

Tensile strength is determined by the thickness of the output and the amount of starch but too much starch can lead to a sticky consistency and took a long time to dry. Based on the results, thinner samples can lead to a low limited and thicker sample can lead to high limited weight.

The product can be dissolved underwater and can dissolve up to 38.18% with an average of 33.316% for 36 hours. Our product is made from fruit waste hence it can degrade up to 5.77% with an average of 4.85% in 100 hours beneath the soil.

Flexibility is determined by the thinness, thickness, and glycerol content. We do not use any fragrance boosters because in this research we only used pasteurization hence bacteria can multiply and can cause unpleasant odor quicker than bioplastic that was sterilized.

The texture can be inconsistent throughout the output hence some parts can be rough or smooth. The texture can be improved by grinding the fruit waste into tinier pieces. Lastly, by these results, the researchers can still improve its overall characteristics from texture consistency, color consistency, and pleasant odor.

Bioplastic can be produced from recycled paper and fruit waste from tangerine, orange, pomelo, lemon, watermelon, melon, unripe and ripe mango with the accurate and right number of additive components.

It has already been proven that some waste from bananas, which are rich in starch, can be used to produce bioplastic (Gaonkar et al., 2017; Millan et al., 2017). Some fruit wastes which have a low amount of starch content like citrus fruits are not used widely to produce bioplastic.

Boiling the fruit peels has a substantial effect in softening the fruit peels. It makes it easier for the blender to shred the fruit peels into smaller pieces. Grinding and reducing the size of the fruit peels are efficient in bonding the mixture. It is very effective when it comes to the stage wherein the mixture is dried up. Additionally, it is easier for the mixture to glue onto each other especially if the fruit peels and papers are as minute as they can be.

Unlike the procedure for orange bioplastic, our method includes water that is already added during the grinding of fruit waste and the addition of starch and glycerol comes after the absorption of excess water. It will be added after because during the absorption of excess water the starch and glycerol might be filtered and therefore be wasted.

Some of the procedures will be imitated like the heating process using an oven, softening fruit peels, and molding the output into thin sheets however, we will apply different approaches in testing our product when it comes to strength. Instead of hooking an object into the product, we hung the product and applied force into it, in this way, we think that the result will be more accurate since it is how we normally use plastic for everyday use.

To begin any project, the researchers need to gather all the materials and equipment needed for the experiments. The researchers can use papers from their finished school task and for fruit peels, for some time, the researchers can gather and store fruit peels from their houses. Before starting the actual experimentation, the researchers need to prepare or to ready all the ingredients and tools to provide convenience in locating the materials. For the ingredients, the researchers need to reduce their size by using wedges, in that case, the heat will easily flow throughout the mixture. The fruit peels must be softened so that they can be ground easily using the blender. The researchers need to grind the recycled papers and fruit peels, in effect, they will be able to be molded into different figures or forms. Water needs to be absorbed so that the heating process will not take so much time. Using a sponge is preferable because it can be used multiple times, unlike tissue. The researchers need to use a container that can withstand the heat inside the oven and a container that will adapt its form. Evaporating the excess liquid in the mixture is the final step before testing the product. After a successful attempt, the researchers are required to test the characteristics of the output. Every failure means a second approach, the researchers will try and repeat the process until we achieve the result the researchers' desire.

Adding paper, specifically, more than 12 percent of the total amount, will only make the output paper-like therefore it is less water-resistant and flexible. Starch is an important ingredient in the mixture, if more starch is added the more tensile it will get. The starch's quantity for every 100 grams of fruit peels is $\frac{1}{8}$ of a cup or 16 grams. The amount of glycerol is enough by 2 ml of glycerol per 25 g of fruit wastes (Ghamande et al., 2018).

The results of the testing of Solubility and Biodegradability are somewhat similar to the study of Marichelvam et al. (2019). Their study's results of the water solubility and biodegradability test and the result of this study are somehow proportional. For the tensile test, the study includes a unique and different way of conducting the test by applying the stress the same way as to how we normally use plastic.

Conclusion

Fruit wastes with none or low starch content are used as a medium to produce bioplastic. In this research, fruit waste and paper are bonded by organic material or starch to make it more tensile and durable to handle objects. The addition of paper produces an output that is more durable and firmer but less flexible and water-resistant. It increases the bond of the fruit wastes making it more tensile as it dries. Starch acts as a glue to hold the bioplastic together.

Adding more starch means increasing its tensile strength but there is an exception. 1/8 cup or 16 grams of starch per 100 grams of fruit waste is certainly enough to produce a bioplastic tensile enough to hold everyday stuff. The proper amount of glycerol is highly required to prevent any waste of glycerol and allows it to dry quicker given that less liquid is added. The amount of glycerol is enough by 2 ml of glycerol per 25 g of fruit wastes. The output of the research is soluble in water and can degrade over some time. The tensile strength of the output reached the expectations of this study.

Given these points, production of bioplastic from fruit wastes such as pomelo peels, watermelon and melon rinds, unripe and ripe mangos, lemon, tangerine, and orange peels as well as recycled paper are possible by discovering the right proportions and proper amounts of additive components. The study is indeed successful in producing bioplastic with waste and recycled materials and able to solve the research problem.

Practical Implication and Recommendations

During the evaporation of liquid, the mixture should come out as smooth as possible to avoid difficulty in flattening or thinning the mixture therefore, fruit wastes and papers are needed to be minute to avoid chunks of fruit waste in the output. Adding more starch into the mixture will increase the output's tensile strength and make it more water-resistant. Paper, on the other hand, will also make it more durable but less water-resistant and flexible. Additionally, if the percentage composition of paper is above 12 percent it will make a paper-like output. The amount of glycerol is enough by 2 ml of glycerol per 25 mg of fruit peels.

Tools and equipment that can be used to flatten the mixture consistently throughout the sheet. Better equipment for thinning the mixture between the parchment papers. Manual work cannot promise a precise and consistent output. The texture is determined by how tiny the fruit waste and paper are. Better equipment for grinding the fruit waste and paper so that the texture can be smoother.

During drying, some parts are not equally cooked. Sometimes, the sides or the middle of the flattened mixture has a different color that determined that it is ready but the different parts are not. Measuring the thickness requires a thickness gauge and identifying the tensile strength requires a testometric machine but those equipment are expensive. Better funding for the research and access to better equipment.

Allocate more time in researching to correctly identify the exact duration the bioplastic will completely degrade and dissolve in water. Use the process called sterilization instead of pasteurization to also prolong its biodegradability and adding fragrance boosters to widen the scope and lessen the limitations.

Drying fruit waste and paper mixture in a silicone rubber mold to produce desired figures, shaping the mixture into utensils, and other forms not limited to the shape of a paper bag are the possible extent.

For the continuation of the research and exploring different characteristics of our product, the following are the possible research continuations:

- Edibility of damaged bioplastic for animals and fertilizer for plants;
- Pre-powdered fruit waste as a relevant input for a different approach in producing bioplastic; and
- Sterilization and adding fragrance in bioplastic synthesis to be used and shaped for food utensils.

References

- Acciona. (n.d.). *What are bioplastics?* https://www.activesustainability.com/environment/what-are-bioplastics/?_adin=02021864894
- Arikan, E. B., & Bilgen, H. D. (2019). Production of bioplastic from potato peel waste and investigation of its biodegradability. *International Advanced Researches and Engineering Journal*, 3(2), 93-97. <https://doi.org/10.35860/iarej.420633>
- European Bioplastics. (2016, March 2). *How can the environmental impact of bioplastics be assessed?* <https://www.european-bioplastics.org/faq-items/how-can-the-environmental-impact-of-bioplastics-be-assessed/>
- Fabunmi, O. O., Tabil, L. G., Chang, P. R., & Panigrahi, S. (2006). *Developing biodegradable plastics from starch* (Paper no. RRV01730). American Society of Agricultural and Biological Engineers. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/242221295_Developing_Biodegradable_Plastics_from_starch
- Gaonkar, M. R., Palaskar, P., & Navandar, R. (2017, December 27-28). *Production of bioplastic from banana peels* (Conference paper). 146th The IIER International Conference, Hong Kong. https://www.worldresearchlibrary.org/up_proc/pdf/1279-15182346031-3.pdf
- Ghamande, M., Kulkarni, A., Shah, N., Kothari, S., & Bhosale, S. (2018). Bio-plastic (Generating plastic from banana peels). In M. V. Ghamande & D. R. Gupta (Eds.), *International conference on new frontiers of engineering, management, social science and humanities* (pp. 39-42). A.R. Research Publication. <http://data.conferenceworld.in/25FebEMSSH/9.pdf>
- Gibbens, S. (2018, November 15). *What you need to know about plant-based plastics*. National Geographic. <https://www.nationalgeographic.com/environment/article/are-bioplastics-made-from-plants-better-for-environment-ocean-plastic>
- Goodall, C. (2011, September 2). *Bioplastics: An important component of global sustainability*. Carbon Commentary. <https://www.carboncommentary.com/blog/2011/09/02/bioplastics-an-important-component-of-global-sustainability>

- Kale, G., Kijchavengkul, T., Auras, R., Rubino, M., Selke, S. E., & Singh, S. P. (2007). Compostability of bioplastic packaging materials: An overview. *Macromolecular Bioscience*, 7(3), 255-277. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mabi.200600168>
- Manimaran, D. S., Nadaraja, K. R., Vellu, J. P., Francisco, V., Kanesen, K., & BinYusoff, Z. (2016). Production of biodegradable plastic from banana peel. *Journal of Petrochemical Engineering*, 1(1), 1-7.
- Marichelvam, M. K., Jawaid, M., & Asim, M. (2019). Corn and rice starch-based bio-plastics as alternative packaging materials. *Fibers*, 7(4), 32. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fib7040032>
- Millan, J. P. G., Bunag, J. M. A., & Cuevas, C. C. A. (2017). Efficacy of Cardava banana (*Musa paradisiaca*) as an alternative component in making biodegradable bio-plastic (Research project). https://www.academia.edu/34003516/FINAL_RESEARCH_PAPER
- Ritchie, H., & Roser, M. (2018, September). *Plastic pollution*. Our World in Data. <https://ourworldindata.org/plastic-pollution>
- The Ocean Cleanup. (n.d.). *The great pacific garbage patch*. <https://theoceancleanup.com/great-pacific-garbage-patch/>